

DEVELOPMENT OF CHILDREN'S SPEECH IN PRE-SCHOOL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract: The main and leading aspect in the development of children's speech in preschool educational institutions is the formation of communicative skills. It is important to apply innovative educational technologies in the process of speech development. The article explores the advantages of effective methods used in the development of children's speech.

Key words: preschool educational institutions, speech development, qualified educator, continuous education.

The use of advanced pedagogical and information technologies in the educational process of preschool educational institutions, the filling of institutions with educators with modern knowledge and the determination of professional qualifications, a sense of creative approach to activities, the reforms carried out in the continuous education system is one of the important directions. As stated in the national personnel training program, qualified educators and pedagogues for the improvement of the preschool education system today need to be in continuous innovative search, think, and also operate based on the formation of advanced ideas in preschool educational institutions.

So, if we provide a comprehensive solution to the problems of the development of speech and communication in the process of adapting children to a preschool educational institution, it is logical to assume that this reduces the adaptation time of students and increases the efficiency of work in this area. In this case, in order to overcome difficulties in the social and intellectual development of the child, it is necessary first of all to develop children's communicative

competence, the ability to build relationships with others using linguistic and interactive techniques.

Speech development of pre-school children is considered an important part of the competence approach to education of children defined in the "First Step" State Curriculum.

First of all, communicative competence, i.e. the formation of the ability to use communication tools in different situations, is defined as the general important competences of a 6-7-year-old child. Therefore, the formation of skills for the growth and development of the child's speech in the content of each educational activity in preschool educational institutions is the main task. Efficiency is high when a child acquires new knowledge based on games and didactic tools. That is, rather than simple reading of fiction, implementation of activities using innovative educational technologies ensures and accelerates the speech development process of each child, thereby helping to improve the quality of education. For this, it is necessary to develop new technologies for the development of preschool children's speech and actively use them in the process.

It was in preschool institutions that, recognizing the incomparable role of fiction in the process of speech development, we observed the high effectiveness of teaching fiction to children with the help of new technologies.

The development of the speech of preschool children is largely related to the correct solution of the following:

- didactic materials for the development of speech regularly include the purposeful speech of parents, educators, fairy tales, poems, songs, stories that are read or told to children;
- modern organization of education using didactic materials;
- to ensure children's active speech communication in educational games.

Thus, we classify the practical advantages of introducing a work of art in an innovative way rather than reading it traditionally. Traditional educational

activities for preschool children recognize that the teacher tells stories, reads, and memorizes by repetition. But experience shows that children repeat the teacher's story with minor changes, the stories are only interpreted using simple words. Therefore, when the process of reading the story ends, it is necessary to ask the children not to retell the story, but to pick the mixed pictures based on this story on the magnetic board according to their place. In the process of finding pictures according to the sequence of events, they develop not only their speech, but also their attention, observation, and logical thinking. Observing the composition of the story they create activates the students and tries to describe it with new words. This activity protects children from boredom, if it is not possible to retell the story of the whole group, this method involves all children in the work process. Especially when the educator changes his status from the role of the main performer to the level of an observer, it gives children freedom.

Based on this, in addition to traditional methods and methods for the formation and activation of coherent speech of preschool children the following innovative technologies are used:

1. Visual modeling technology
2. IC technologies

1. Visual modeling is effective in teaching preschool children. Using this method, the teacher and the child describe objects, events, actions, concepts, episodes using simplified schematic images and symbols. Visual modeling is a way of conveying various knowledge to children stands out as. It is also successfully used as a means of developing their intellectual and speech skills. The above-mentioned game "Find the place of the pictures" is an example of visual modeling.

2. Psychologists say that any new information presented to children on a computer, on a big screen, is attractive. Today's children sometimes learn information faster with the help of computer technology than if they simply hear it. One example is that he can remember the characters of the story he heard, but he remembers the characters of the cartoon for a long time. Therefore, the need to use

ICT in preschool education today is clear. The use of ICT in the educational process for the development of speech offers a wide range of opportunities. In particular, listening to the text of an artistic work using electronic resources is more effective for children than a monotonous story. Because adding music and using tools such as the sound of birds, water, and wind in an electronic resource ensures the effectiveness of the text. Children respond to texts listened to on the basis of ICT with presence and interest. Considering that the main tasks of speech development - enriching and activating the vocabulary, forming the grammatical structure of speech, teaching coherent speech are solved in the preschool age, special attention should be paid to creative educational technologies. In particular, it is necessary to pay attention to richly equipping the activity center for speech development with artistic manuals and didactic materials. It is the educator's responsibility to create a methodical bank consisting of sets of pictures with plots suitable for the topic, sets of toys intended for staging, and printed didactic games aimed at developing all aspects of children's speech. Recognizing that exposure to fiction plays an important role in the development of speech, it is important to organize book corners and " a smart book shelf" in groups. Because the pupils get to know new impressions, knowledge, and skills directly with such materials. It is in a favorable environment for the formation of dialogic, emotionally rich speech. As the children's speech and thinking develop with the help of works of art, at the same time they enter into a connected dialogue and begin to express their thoughts. It gives the child pleasure and joy, these feelings make speech active the most powerful that stimulates perception and creates independent speech activity is a tool. When we observe this in practice, when speech training sessions are conducted based on games and effective educational technologies, children are active, express their thoughts boldly, do not get bored in the process, use new words in their vocabulary, and due to their interest, they are eager to learn new information it became known. This is the main and necessary requirement for the formation of generally important competencies in the preparation of children for

school education in preschool institutions. . Because the introduction of innovations into the work of the preschool educational organization is the most important condition for improving and reforming the preschool education system.

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